

PYTHON DASTURLASH TILI IMKONIYATLARI

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dasturlash tilining imkoniyatlari

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Kalit soʻzlar : Python , Python dasturlash tilining oʻziga xosligi, Python

Ushbu ilmiy maqolada Python dasturlash tilining boshqa dasturlash tillaridan sodda va kengayuvchanligini koʻrib chiqamiz .Python dasturlash tili imkoniyatlari kengayishiga moyil boʻlgan dasturiy til hisoblanadi.. Bundan tashqari, Python juda ham koʻp, foydali hamda xilma-xil dasturlar kutubxonalarga egaligi ham juda muhimdir.

Python – bu oʻrganishga oson va shu bilan birga imkoniyatlari yuqori boʻlgan oz sonlik zamonaviy dasturlash tillari qatoriga kiradi. Python yuqori darajadagi ma'lumotlar strukturasi va oddiy lekin samarador obyektga yo'naltirilgan dasturlash uslublarini taqdim etadi.

Pythonning oʻziga xosligi

Oddiy, oʻrganishga oson, sodda sintaksisga ega, dasturlashni boshlash uchun qulay, erkin va ochiq kodlik dasturiy ta'minot. Dasturni yozish davomida quyi darajadagi detallarni, misol uchun xotirani boshqarishni hisobga olish shart emas. Ko'plab platformalarda hech qanday o'zgartirishlarsiz ishlay oladi.

Interpretatsiya(Интерпретируемый) qilinadigan til. Kengayishga (Расширяемый) moyil til. Agar dasturni biror joyini tezroq ishlashini xoxlasak shu qismni C yoki C++ dasturlash tillarida yozib keyin shu qismni python kodi orqali ishga tushirsa(chaqirsa) bo'ladi.

Juda ham ko'p xilma-xil kutubxonalarga ega.

xml/html fayllar bilan ishlash

http so'rovlari bilan ishlash

GUI(grafik interfeys)

Web ssenariy tuzish

FTP bilan ishlash

Rasmi audio video fayllar bilan ishlash

Robot texnikada

Matematik va ilmiy hisoblashlarni programmalash

Pythonni katta projeklarda ishlatish mumkin. Chunki, uni chegarasi yoʻq, imkoniyati yuqori. Shuningdek, u sodda va universalligi bilan programmalash tillari orasida eng yaxshisidir.

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